

Milestone: M6.3 Project website is live

Lead Participant: ELIXIR Hub

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Due: 31 Jul 2020

Date Of Completion: 31 JUL 2020

Means of Verification

Project website: <https://b1mg-project.eu/>

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

No

Project participants & others

ELIXIR Hub: Martin cook, Xenia Perez, Andrew Smith, Nikki Coutts, Corinne Martin, Serena Scollen, Juan Arenas.

B1MG-OG: B1MG WP Leaders and 1+MG WG Leaders

Next action steps

- Link to stakeholders portal
- Continuous improvement
 - Analyse web site metrics.

B1MG has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 951724